

NET-Fuels D6.2 deliverable report

Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan

Dissemination Level: Public

**NET- Fuels | INCREASING BIOMASS CONVERSION EFFICIENCY TO
CARBON-NEGATIVE SUSTAINABLE BIOFUELS BY COMBINATION OF
THERMOCHEMICAL AND BIO-ELECTROCHEMICAL PROCESSES**

HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-09 | GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER: 101083780

Deliverable D6.2:

Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan

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NET-Fuels consortium

Short	Beneficiary	Role
UNIBO	Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna	CO
FRA	Fraunhofer UMSICHT	BEN
LEITAT	Acondicionamiento Tarrasense (LEITAT)	BEN
SUT	Silesian University of Technology	BEN
ITHAKA	Ithaka Institute	BEN
REACH	REACH Innovation	BEN
WRG	WRG Europe	AP

CO...Coordinator, BEN...Beneficiary, AP...Associated Partner

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Executive Summary

This document describes the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation strategies and plan to be carried out by the NET-Fuels project. D6.2 delivers the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CD&E) preliminary strategy, in order to communicate the project results, raise the profile of the NET-Fuels process and secure project awareness among relevant peers, as well as to support commercial and policymaker interest (for subsequent technology maturation (TRL 7) projects).

D6.2 can be seen as a ‘living document’ that represents for all partners a reference for the communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy and activities of the project. It will be regularly updated, as necessary. New versions may be internally released in order to ensure alignment and coherence at a consortium level. Updated versions of this document (submitted in M6) will be submitted via the EC portal as D6.3 and D6.4 at M16 and M36, as indicated below:

- D6.2 - Dissemination, exploitation and communication plan (M6, April 2023)
- D6.3 - First dissemination, exploitation and communication report (M16, February 2024)
- D6.4 - Second dissemination, exploitation and communication report (M36, October 2025)

Figure 1: Overall plan of NET-Fuels deliverables and lead partners

1 Introduction

1.1 Main Purpose

A comprehensive Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CD&E) plan is fundamental to ensuring maximum impact of the NET-Fuels project by supporting the outputs from the project (e.g.: deliverables and key-exploitable results (KERs)). Identifying target audiences and creating tailored information to engage and share with these audiences will put the necessary steps and actions in place to facilitate the future (post-project) maturation of the technology to pre-commercial scale and, ultimately, to full commercial implementation.

For the purposes of this deliverable at this early stage in the project, this document is a first draft of the intentions for CD&E and the anticipated routes that will be taken to maximise impact. This plan is a living document and will be updated and amended as new information and data is acquired, with further reports and planning updates on CD&E activities delivered at Months 16 (D6.3) and 36 (D6.4).

1.2 Contributions of Partners & Responsibilities

WP6 is led by WRG Europe with extensive support from REACH (primarily for exploitation). This Work Package is also strongly dependent and interrelated to WP5 “Business Development and Potential Industrial Scale-up” led by REACH. The relationship of the Work Packages within NET-Fuels is shown in Figure 2. Work Package 6 overarches all the project activities.

Figure 2: PERT chart showing interaction between NET-Fuels Work Packages

The leader of WP6, WRG Europe (Mark Langley), will act as Dissemination and Exploitation Officer for the project and General Assembly (GA) with input and support from the Coordinator and Beneficiaries. WRG Europe will oversee the CD&E strategy for the project, will coordinate related activities, with REACH (responsible for the project’s Exploitation strategy) liaising with beneficiaries regarding industrial opportunities and exploitation of outputs, including protection of intellectual property.

All partners are expected to contribute to CD&E activities. They will be involved in more detailed annual planning (e.g.: see Gantt chart in Annex 1) where they will input into required digital media for the project including giving feedback on media layout (e.g.: flyers and posters), video storyboards, social media strategy and posting, and content for (e.g.: articles and blogs) and upgrades to the project website. Partners will also identify relevant conferences, scientific journals, and trade/industry magazines to contribute to via articles, presentations, and papers. A log will be kept via the project SharePoint of all publications so these can be reported to Commission via the Portal as part of the periodic reporting activity.

2 Objectives and Expected Impacts

2.1 Objectives

The Work Package 6 specific objectives, as taken from the Grant Agreement, are as follows:

Objective 6.1: Develop and continuously update the dissemination, communication, and exploitation plan.

Objective 6.2: Communicate the project results.

Objective 6.3: Deliver the dissemination strategy.

Objective 6.4: Deliver the exploitation strategy.

These objectives will be achieved through the following four Work Package tasks:

Task 6.1: Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities (led by WRG) [M1-M6]

Task 6.2: Communication activities (led by WRG) [M1-M48]

Task 6.3: Dissemination of project results (led by WRG) [M1-M48]

Task 6.4: Exploitation Plan and strategic actions (led by REACH) [M1-M48]

These tasks are associated with the four primary deliverables of the project, namely:

Deliverable 6.1: Website and project branding (M4)

Deliverable 6.2: Dissemination, exploitation and communication plan (M6)

Deliverable 6.3: First dissemination, exploitation and communication report (M16)

Deliverable 6.4: Second dissemination, exploitation and communication report (M36)

The objectives and impacts will be achieved by delivering the CD&E plans, with initial activities shown in Annex 1. This high-level plan, which will be updated annually, is accompanied by a more granular short-term plan that will cover a 6–12-month period in the project (see also Annex 1).

2.2 Expected Outcomes and Impacts

The expected outcomes from NET-Fuels for which this plan is constructed to support and maximise are as follows:

1. Validation of the industrial pilot in Year 4.
2. At least **1 Innovation Action** to scale up the system and prove biomass conversion efficiency to advanced biofuels at 55%, in connection with and a refinery/chemical park/district, bio-hub or industrial site.
3. At least **1 Innovation Action** to show the versatility of use of the component unit operation (interoperability): application downstream a biogas digester.
4. At least **1 Innovation Action** to show the application of the biobattery/P2G principle measuring the chemical energy stored by NET-Fuels.
5. Increased biochar production.
6. Improvement of carbon sink “Market” (new certificate emission).
7. Intensification of awareness for exploitation of the residue valorisation pathway for the prosumers target group.

Secondly, the estimated impacts from NET-Fuels for which this plan is also constructed to support and maximise are as follows:

1. **25±9 Mtoe/year** of advanced biofuels production. Negative carbon intensity of biofuels: 80-110 gCO₂eq per MJ biofuels.
2. **6.7% ± 2.5% advanced fuel share** of final consumption over total fuel consumption.
3. **110±50 Mt/year of CO₂** of net negative emission.

4. **65±9 Mt/year** of biochar: massive biochar production reinforcing carbon conservative agriculture (CAP-Next Generation EU policies).
5. Advanced fuels costs: **70±30 €/MWh (improving EUSGAB estimate 83-118 of €/MWh)**.
6. **95-99%** of the biogenic carbon used in fuels and biochar.
7. Increased acceptance of advanced biofuels.
8. Increase knowledge of the technology deployment in medium-long term.

To achieve these outcomes and impacts requires the project to ensure mechanisms are in place (e.g.: securing interested stakeholder for follow-up projects) to sustain the project outputs past the end of the project. This is discussed in the following sections.

3 Communication Plan

3.1 Target Groups and Audiences

The objectives, key exploitable results, and important outcomes of NET-Fuels will be communicated and disseminated freely (after IP protection when required) to inform target audiences of the scientific, economic, and social value of NET-Fuels.

The following generic target audiences have been identified:

- The general public: To inform them about the NET-Fuels technologies and the importance of advanced sustainable fuels and energy to the overall mix of clean energy solutions for transport and other sectors.
- Industrial stakeholders: To establish organisations (large industry and SMEs) interested in furthering the technology after completion of the project (e.g.: with future projects and -ultimately- commercial adoption).
- The research and innovation community: To establish organisations with a particular focus on: (a) research in sustainable fuels, soil enhancement, and waste conversion; and (b) chemical processes capable of developing sustainable energy alternatives which can support the maturation of the project through to commercial demonstration and adoption.
- Policymakers and standards bodies: To support the necessary standardisation of chemical processes and soil enhancement to allow regulated commercial application.

In general terms we can break down the types of engagement for each target audience as per Table 1:

Table 1: NET-Fuels Target Audiences

Type	Target Groups	Tools	Type of Engagement
Project media creation and distribution	Industry and SME. Researchers. Policy and standards. General public.	Project Corporate Identity: Logo and identity, MS Office templates used as a common public identity for all management, communication and dissemination activities. The project logo will be implemented on all media.	Material: Project leaflet, promotional flyers for target stakeholders, additional promotional flyers for open events, scientific posters, project roll-up, project newsletters highlighting key results.

Digital media and social platforms	<p>Industry and SME.</p> <p>Researchers.</p> <p>Policy and standards.</p> <p>General public.</p>	<p>A public website integrated with NET-Fuels activities, including informative content, news and events, video animations, and integrated social media accounts. The project will map appropriate communication channels, individuals and organisations, user communities to include in the NET-Fuels network.</p>	<p>Material: Digital awareness campaigns, events and networks to help redirect to the website where data and information can be accessed. Regular social media activity will also help to generate followers.</p>
Scientific and technical publications	<p>Researchers.</p> <p>Industry and SME.</p>	<p>Scientific papers will be published to inform scientific communities and potential users about NET-Fuels achievements. Publications will be through high-ranking, peer-reviewed multidisciplinary journals and more specialised peer-reviewed international journals. Technical papers and application specific results will be published in trade journals and media, targeting end user groups. All publications will be available via open access channels. Gold open access will be the default standard unless data and/or IP prevents this. In any case publications will be made available via public online repositories and the projects webpage.</p>	<p>Material: social media campaigns alerting target groups to new publications; lay summaries for industry and SMEs highlighting new outputs.</p>
Conferences, Workshops, Trade fairs, Symposia	<p>Industry and SME.</p> <p>Researchers.</p> <p>Policy and standards.</p> <p>General public</p>	<p>The consortium will define important international conferences to be attended by its members to present the latest achievements, to discuss progress, developments and challenges in this field, and to find new industrial partners.</p>	<p>Events: Such as EU Sustainable Energy Week, European Biomass Conference, and EUBCE.</p> <p>Also, to reduce travel costs the consortium plans to organise, where possible, consortium meetings in conjunction with these conferences</p> <p>Material: Project leaflets, factsheets, promotional flyers, scientific posters, promo roll-up, newsletter on final results.</p>
Press and Media	<p>Industry and SME.</p> <p>Researchers.</p>	<p>Press releases will be made at relevant points in the project such as interim results and key achievement, or for activities and events. Additionally, press and media representative will be invited to the final project PR event.</p>	<p>Material: press releases (EN), press releases translated by beneficiaries</p>

	General public		
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Table 1 is purposely generic because specificity will be added as part of the CD&E activities within the first year of the project. To support the refinement and definition of target audiences, a **stakeholder mapping** exercise will be undertaken within the first half of 2023. Meetings will be held with partners to discuss key conferences to attend, contacts they have that could support dissemination and exploitation activities (including future scale up), industrial networks that the project could link into, other related projects, and relevant policy and standards bodies to support future commercial adoption. The stakeholder mapping exercise will define a list of contacts against the audience titles of “industry and SME”, “research and innovation”, “general public”, and “policy and standards”.

3.2 Maximising Reach Through Partner Networking and Clustering

The stakeholder mapping activity discussed above will support network and clustering. This will bring together not just relevant networks, but also related projects (EU-funded or otherwise) for co-creation and mutual benefit and achievement of outcomes. For example, Annex 2 shows some examples of related EU projects with which NET-Fuels could potentially collaborate. This will be updated and enhanced as part of the CD&E detailed planning for 2023 (see Gantt chart in Annex 1).

3.3 Horizon Results Platform and Results Booster

Another key pipeline to support dissemination and exploitation is the Horizon Results Platform, which is available through the EC Portal. As the project progresses, the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) that are discussed in Section 5 (and others that may occur during the project) will be uploaded to the Portal. These will then be accessible to other projects, researchers, industry, policymakers, etc., who might be interested in using the results for collaborative purposes. Moreover, the project will subscribe to the Horizon Results Booster. Specifically:

WRG Europe:

- **Service 1: Portfolio Dissemination & Exploitation Strategy (PDES):**
 - **Module A**, Identifying and creating the portfolio of R&I project results
 - **Module B**, Helping projects from the portfolio to design and execute a portfolio dissemination plan

REACH Innovation:

- **Service 1: Portfolio Dissemination & Exploitation Strategy (PDES):**
 - **Module C**, Assisting projects to improve their existing exploitation strategy
- **Service 2: Business Plan Development (BPD)**

This will help substantially augment the capacity of the project to promote and exploit its technologies and project results.

3.4 NET-Fuels Branding

It is important that the project creates a strong identity that stakeholders can recognise and trust as well as CD&E activities are implemented regularly to maintain awareness and interest.

At the outset of the project, NET-Fuels branding was conceptualised by a graphic designer working for WRG Europe. A colour palette was put together and complementary fonts selected. Several versions of the logo were presented at the kick-off meeting, including suggestions from beneficiaries and the favourite was chosen by majority vote (Figure 3).

This logo will appear on all NET-Fuels documentation, social media, webpages, and promotional material. In addition to the NET-Fuels logo, the colour palette will be used across all dissemination and communication material. All media will contain the necessary acknowledgement/declaration of EU-funding and disclaimers relating to authors' views.

Figure 3: Project logos/icon and colour palette

3.5 Templates

A set of templates for NET-Fuels documentation (reports, minutes, etc.) and presentations have been developed using the colour palette above and circulated to the beneficiaries. As stated above, the templates carry the NET-Fuels logo, EU flag, and wording acknowledging EU-funding and disclaimers. Deliverables, reports, and other documentation will also use these templates (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Document templates (PowerPoint -left and Word -right)

3.6 Project Website

A dedicated NET-Fuels website (Figure 5) has been designed and built by WRG Europe (see <https://www.netfuelsproject.org>). The website will be managed by WRG Europe throughout the duration of NET-Fuels (and for 1 year after the completion of the project), with regular updates on progress in the form

of news items, articles (or blogs), information on events, informational videos, updates from related projects and initiatives, and an annual newsletter. It should be noted that the use of the .org domain is a result of the UK leaving the EU (“Brexit”) and that UK organisations such as WRG Europe are no longer able to register and use .eu domains. To get around this problem, one of the EU partners within the project will purchase the .eu domain and will set up a redirect to the .org site. This means that all project dissemination and communication material can use the .eu URL to be consistent with other EU projects.

Figure 5: Project website homepage

The website uses the NET-Fuels colour scheme and makes full use of all branding. It was released for the beneficiaries to review and was subsequently modified based on feedback. The website is the primary means by which industrial organisations, the scientific community, policymakers, and the public can find out about work being carried out by the consortium.

As the project develops, the website will link to websites of other related projects and networks, fostering relationships for the mutual benefit of these projects or networks. The website will also share posts and links for relevant articles and events from related projects to support wider understanding of the research and commercial landscapes within which NET-Fuels is functioning.

The website will act as a repository for documents and articles for both private NET-Fuels members only (i.e.: via SharePoint logins) and public (non-sensitive) consumption (e.g.: public level deliverable reports). Printable promotional material for use at conferences and events (e.g.: flyers, posters, brochures) will be available for download.

The website will contain a sign-up area for the NET-Fuels newsletter (and this will be enhanced to include mailshots for important updates). At present, the sign-up area is inactive, as WRG Europe is reviewing recent updates to GDPR regulations to ensure data is handled correctly.

3.7 Social Media

The NET-Fuels project is represented on three social media platforms: LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube.

3.7.1 LinkedIn

At the beginning of the project, WRG Europe set up a NET-Fuels LinkedIn account (Figure 6). Posts on LinkedIn will be aimed mainly at professional organisations (i.e., academia and industry), focussing on events, results, and exploitable outputs.

Account Link: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/netfuels/>.

Figure 6: NET-Fuels LinkedIn homepage

3.7.2 Twitter

A dedicated Twitter account has been set up and is managed by WRG Europe (Figure 7). While Twitter is also good for reaching academic and industrial organisations, it is more appropriate for public outreach and engagement (compared to LinkedIn). Appropriate hashtags and use of promoted posts will help reach wider and targeted audiences.

Account Link: https://twitter.com/NETFuels_HEU.

Figure 7: NET-Fuels Twitter homepage

3.7.3 YouTube

YouTube is an excellent platform to share longer-form visual content from the project, such as videos, recorded presentations, and vlogs. A YouTube channel has not been set up yet, as no content has been created, but as soon as this becomes available the channel will be launched.

3.8 Other e-resources

3.8.1 Newsletters

An e-newsletter will be published annually. Targeted at sector-specific industrial and academic organisations, the e-newsletter will provide information about the project, updates on results, and potentially exploitable outcomes. The e-newsletter will be written in a style that is accessible to multiple audiences in terms of technical detail and complexity. It will be made available via the website (and advertised via social media) as well as to those who have signed up from the website.

3.8.2 Press/Trade Releases

Four press releases will be created by the end of each project year. These will be made available on the website, but magazines or online that might be interested in publishing the press release will also be approached. This includes the EU's Horizon Magazine.

3.8.3 Informational Videos

A suite of informational videos will be prepared by WRG Europe and shared via social media. These will be available on the project website and YouTube channel, in due course. Animated videos are an invaluable means for delivering simplified information on the project to a range of audiences.

Videos will include:

1. Overview of the project using animation/motion graphics;
2. Specific technical videos on innovations within the project.
3. Filming (e.g. validation sites) and interviews

3.8.4 Brochure and Poster

To promote the NET-Fuels project, a brochure and poster will be created within the first year. These will be distributed electronically but will be available for printing and distribution at events and conferences. Both the brochure and poster will be reviewed and updated as the project progresses.

4 Dissemination

Dissemination of NET-Fuels results is vital for the project to achieve lasting impact. Going beyond engaging target audiences and communicating project objectives and methods, NET-Fuels' dissemination measures will raise awareness of project outputs. These activities will highlight the importance of the NET-Fuels technologies and show how outputs can be adopted and exploited beyond the project funding period. NET-Fuels dissemination is tailored to generate maximum awareness of the project among industrial beneficiaries, investors, government bodies, potential customers, and stakeholders in addition to academics and research organisations (e.g.: to create further research opportunities/projects). Public engagement will continue with the dual aims of building trust among potential users and imparting NET-Fuels results to interested parties.

4.1 Internal and external dissemination

There are two strands to NET-Fuels dissemination: internal and external. Internal activities will consist primarily of creating awareness of exploitable results within the consortium by effective management. The project management team will seek pathways to exploit results including taking the technology to pre-

commercial demonstration scale. At project meetings, there will be a reoccurring agenda item to discuss key exploitable results and how they can be advanced, including any necessary intellectual property protection. Regular management communications will also announce important achievements to the consortium and all documents will be available on the project SharePoint drive.

External dissemination activities will engage those outside the project around key exploitable results, and includes user communities in academia and industry, and other stakeholders such as the public, policymakers, and government agencies. External dissemination will take three main forms:

- 1) Attendance and exhibitions at relevant conferences and trade events.
- 2) Open days and events.
- 3) Publishing papers in relevant peer-reviewed scientific and trade journals.

All dissemination activities will be supplemented by targeted media campaigns aimed at informing as wide an audience as possible about NET-Fuels and project outputs including technology developments. Project updates and news on non-sensitive results will be submitted to general and trade magazines, news media, and visual and audio media outlets. Condensed updates will be shared on social media and the NET-Fuels website (in the form of news items and articles).

4.2 Conference attendance and exhibitions

Conference attendance and exhibition at conferences (e.g.: in trade halls) is an important dissemination mechanism. Through its experienced consortium, the project will identify key conferences and/or sector-specific trade shows as part of ongoing CD&E activity where important outputs can be presented (this could include EUBCE, EU Sustainable Energy Week, and the European Biomass Conference). Conferences will be selected on appropriateness of themes and opportunities for the consortium to disseminate information to the most relevant audiences.

4.3 Publishing papers

It is envisaged that around 10 peer-reviewed papers will be published in high-quality journals over the lifetime of NET-Fuels. The authors of peer-reviewed papers will acknowledge the NET-Fuels project and the financial support provided by the EU. All published papers will be recorded in an Excel log in order to update the Commission during financial reporting periods. Links to the NET-Fuels website will be provided on the website of the publishing journal for people to follow (“backlinks”) to learn more about the project overall. The spreadsheets on dissemination reporting, publications, communications, and publications/scientific papers will be available at the NET-Fuels SharePoint repository.

4.3.1 Open access and data management

Where appropriate, papers will be published using the newly established European Commission’s Open Access publishing platform ORE, (see about ORE via: <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>), Zenodo or equivalent trustful open repository as specified in NET-Fuels DMP Deliverable D1.2 [7]. This allows rapid, free, and open access publication, enabling others to build quickly upon new ideas, whilst maximising the impact and of research outcomes to the Commission, the scientific and industrial communities, and the general public.

All data generated by NET-Fuels will be centrally stored (for access and retrieval) on the project SharePoint using standard archiving data control procedures. Data will be backed up on to secure areas of a central server designated for this purpose. Moreover, where appropriate, data will also be stored on the Zenodo open repository maintained by CERN. As specified in NET-Fuels DMP, guided by REACH, Data storage will follow the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable) principles, which recognises the need to

balance openness and protection of potentially commercially sensitive information. As such, all due consideration will be given to IPR, security, and privacy concerns associated with distributing project results prior to any external dissemination.

All data management activities will be handled by REACH within the WP1-Task T1.3.

4.4 Networking and Clustering

As mentioned in Section 3.2, the stakeholder mapping and clustering activities will create a broad base of contacts relevant to the project. Links with networks and clustering created during the project will be essential to maximise dissemination reach and impacts thereof.

The planned Exploitation Strategy (see section 5) will also contribute to grow the project's network along its lifetime, via the continuous efforts that are planned to be done on the interested stakeholders community.

5 Exploitation Plan

5.1 Introduction to NET-Fuels Exploitation

Attending objective O6.4 (O6.4: Deliver the exploitation strategy) of our project [1], the preliminary *NET-Fuels Exploitation Plan (EP)* was elaborated by REACH as part of its work within WP6 task 6.4 (T6.4: Exploitation Plan and strategic actions) and was embedded in this deliverable D6.2 (Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan) in month M6, organized by WRG within the overall work of the work package WP6. The EP will be regularly updated as required, according to the project developments, throughout its lifetime.

The main objective of this preliminary Exploitation Plan is to define the exploitation strategy concepts for NET-Fuels, which will consider among other aspects the analysis of the exploitation potential for the project results, in order to maximize the impact of the project outcomes, beyond and during the lifetime of the project.

For achieving its goals, the preliminary EP presents the activities planned to ensure an effective exploitation of the project results. The EP strategic activities will mainly promote the project's Key Exploitable Results (KERs) to their target market.

In the long run, the EP will further consider in detail the following features: (a) the identification of the Intellectual Property (IP); (b) the assessment of the expected socioeconomic and environmental impact of the generated knowledge and technology; (c) the identification of the possible technical and non-technical barriers to the exploitation of the project results; (d) the methodology and strategy for the appropriated management of the knowledge generated in the project and IP protection; (e) the analysis of the exploitation potential of the project results; (f) the individual exploitation plans including cost-benefit feasibility; and (g) the consolidation of an ecosystem of communities of practice for the project, including industrial partners and interested stakeholders, aiming at promoting the project's individual KERs and the overall NET-Fuels solution via the organized T6.4 exploitation activities.

In this document, the preliminary NET-Fuels Exploitation Plan specifies how the different tasks and activities related to exploitation will be led and structured, emphasizing the following aspects:

- The identification of the target groups more focused on the project's exploitation.
- The project's KERs, as defined initially at proposal level, which will serve as the basis for the initial exploitation activities.
- The exploitation strategy and how the different activities to be taken to achieve the market uptake.
- The intellectual property management.
- The initial plan for the roadmap to market uptake.
- The project's exploitation management and monitoring.

5.2 Target Group Identification for Exploitation

The target group for the NET-Fuels Exploitation Plan is based on the one defined for the project's Dissemination Plan (see section 3.1 Target Groups and Audiences), with focus on stakeholders that are more suitable to support the project's exploitation phase. Besides the project's Advisory Board (ESAB), it includes large industrial stakeholders and SMEs, Prosumers, the Research Community (R&D international stakeholders and universities), refineries, agricultural and forestry sector-organizations, operators of biogas plants, automotive industry companies, plant manufacturers, high CO₂ emitters (iron & steel and cement industries), chemical and oil & gas industries, wastewater treatment plants, as well as policy makers and legislature, national and regional bodies, NGOs, and organizations from private and public sectors at national and European levels.

5.2.1 ESAB

As stated in [1, 2], the Exploitation Stakeholders and Advisory Board (ESAB), appointed and steered by the NET-Fuels General Assembly (GA), shall be consulted within NET-Fuels implementation phase to facilitate the decisions of the GA and to provide advice on specific project activities and tasks.

The ESAB is composed of a representative set of stakeholders, including companies interested in the exploitation of biomasses, energy companies, research organizations and one refinery.

The main role of the ESAB is to provide guidance and advice on the exploitation and commercialization of the project outcomes, ensuring that they are maximized and disseminated effectively to the appropriate stakeholders and leading to greater impact and long-term sustainability.

At proposal level, the international organizations (and network initiatives) listed in the table below have expressed interest in following the implementation and exploitation of the NET-Fuels project as members of the ESAB. The initial ESAB list, as in [1], embedded 9 organizations (1-9). Recent networking activities undertaken by REACH in South America has established a new contact added to ESAB initial list at position 10 (see Table 2: NET-Fuels ESAB Members), namely: Grupo Marca Ambiental¹ in Brazil, a waste/residuals valorization organization that is interested in following up the development of NET-Fuels project for potential synergies and adoption of the project results. The ESAB list will be continuously expanded during the project, as more stakeholders commit their interest to NET-Fuels’ development and outcomes.

Table 2: NET-Fuels ESAB Members

#	ESAB Organizations	Country	Stakeholder / AB Member
1	Caviro EXTRA	Italy	AB
2	Botanic Garden (Research Institution of the Polish Academy of Science)	Poland	AB
3	European Biochar Industry (EBI)	Germany	AB
4	European Energy Research Alliance (EERA)	Belgium	AB
5	ENI-REWIND	Italy	AB
6	BAYERNOIL Raffineriegesellschaft mbH	Germany	AB
7	SUNCOR Energy	Canada	AB
8	CO ₂ Value Europe	Belgium	AB
9	Consorzio Italiano Biogas (CIB)	Italy	AB
10	Grupo Marca Ambiental (waste valorization group)	Brazil	Stakeholder

REACH plans to maintain within the “NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book” (see section 5.4.2), an updated list of the organizations connected with the project, including ESAB members, with their level of interest and engagement with NET-Fuels’ exploitation. Figure 8 illustrates the ESAB Worksheet that can be found in the preliminary version of the NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book.

¹ <https://marcaambiental.com.br/>

#	ESAB Organizations	Country	Stakeholder / AB Member	URL	Main Interest	Contact Person	Partner Contact
1	Caviro EXTRA	Italy	Advisory Board (AB)				UNIBO
2	Botanic Garden (Research Institution of the Polish Academy of Science)	Poland	AB				SUT
3	European Biochar Industry (EBI)	Germany	AB				FRA
4	European Energy Research Alliance (EERA)	Belgium	AB				LEITAT
5	ENI-REWIND	Italy	AB				UNIBO
6	BAYERNOIL Raffineriegesellschaft mbH	Germany	AB				FRA
7	SUNCOR Energy	Canada	AB				
8	CO ₂ Value Europe	Belgium	AB				LEITAT
9	Consorzio Italiano Biogas (CIB)	Italy	AB				UNIBO
10	Grupo Marca Ambiental (waste valorization group)	Brazil	Stakeholder			Átila	REACH (Fatima Dargam)
11							
12							

Figure 8: Screenshot Detail of the NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book (ESAB Worksheet).

The Exploitation Strategy presented here (see section 5.4) will control the way that the Exploitation Stakeholders and Advisory Board will contribute to the overall achievement of the exploitation results defined for the project.

5.3 NET-Fuels Planned Project Results

The *Project Results* (PRs) identified for NET-Fuels in [1] were classified as Common and Individual Key Exploitable Results (KERs), based respectively on a common exploitation perspective, considering the overall solution of the project, and on an individual exploitation perspective per partner.

5.3.1 NET-Fuels Common KER

The overall common KER exploitation will consider NET-Fuels Integrated prototype with auxiliary systems, combining key-technologies for carbon-negative biofuel production, as well as its system analysis, techno-economic feasibility and market study to scale-up (see Table 3).

Table 3: NET-Fuels Overall Common Key-Exploitable Result

NET-Fuels Common KER
Integrated prototype with auxiliary systems combining key-technologies for carbon-negative biofuel production , system analysis, techno-economic feasibility, and market study to deploy the project at a higher scale (including densification and drying facilities for feedstock pre-treatment).

Owners of the NET-Fuels Common KER will be “All Partners” with the following planned exploitation routes and goals:

- Validation of one industrial pilot based on project results.
- At least 1 Innovation Action (IA) to scale up the system and prove biomass conversion efficiency at 55% in connection with an industrial site (refinery/chemical park/district).

- Validation of the production of advanced biofuels with negative emissions.
- At least 1 IA to show the versatility of use of the components (interoperability), e.g.: application downstream a biogas digester.
- At least 1 IA to show the application of the biobattery /P2G principle to measure the stored chemical energy.
- At least 1 IA on energy storage coupled to one renewable energy production park.
- Increased biochar production & Improvement of carbon sink “Market” (new certificate emission).
- Intensification of awareness for exploitation of the residuals & valorisation pathway for the prosumers target group.

5.3.2 NET-Fuels Individual KERs

Exploitation per partner of Individual KERs is going to happen among the partners in NET-Fuels, as they have their own interests and perspective on how to benefit from the developments, services, know-how and work experience gained with the project.

Table 4 below summarizes the Individual Key Exploitable Results (KERs) specific to each consortium partner, as in [1], with initially defined exploitation paths.

Table 4: Summary of the NET-Fuels Key-Exploitable Results per Partner

Individual KERs	Potential Use & Applications	Potential Users
<p>UNIBO Assessment framework to estimate the environmental consequences engendered by the gradual implementation of negative biofuel technology from secondary resources.</p> <p>Negative emission accounting tools and related datasets and inventory database.</p> <p>System dynamics modelling to account for the use of renewable energy in power-to-gas systems.</p>	<p>Consultancy</p> <p>Advisory services</p> <p>Contribution to policies</p>	<p>Public sectors,</p> <p>Regional Bodies,</p> <p>JRC, ETIP.</p>
<p>FRAUNHOFER (FRA) Validated thermo-chemical conversion system at TRL 5 including oxy-combustion of TCR-tailgas, (production of H₂ according to standard (ISO14687) from TCR-gas.</p> <p>Production of clean CO₂ from oxyfuel combustion for downstream synthesis.</p> <p>Solution for internal process heating of TCR by process heat from oxy-combustion.</p>	<p>Application in combination with different biogenic gaseous fuels (biogas, pyrolysis gas, etc.).</p> <p>Enabling the use of biogenic gases for CO₂ based production of biofuels.</p>	<p>Refineries Agricultural and Forestry sector,</p> <p>Operators of biogas plants,</p> <p>Automotive Industry,</p> <p>Plant manufacturers.</p>
<p>LEITAT Validated bio electrochemical methanation (BEM) system at TRL 5, for CO₂ conversion to CH₄ at pilot scale.</p> <p>Integration of the pilot reactor with TCR and oxyfuel processes.</p>	<p>Enabling the use of biogenic gases for CO₂ based production of biofuels.</p> <p>1 patent on pilot plant BEM technology.</p>	<p>High CO₂ emitters (Iron & Steel and cement Industry),</p> <p>chemical and oil & gas industries,</p> <p>Waste water Treatment plants.</p>

<p>SUT</p> <p>Validated CFD models of oxy-combustion of lean gases containing pollutants such as tars.</p>	<p>Biomass based conversion technologies.</p> <p>Biomass residues utilization.</p> <p>Waste to energy and waste incineration technologies.</p>	<p>Industrial & Research Organizations,</p> <p>SMEs community,</p> <p>Private & Public Sector,</p> <p>R&D International Stakeholders.</p>
<p>ITHAKA</p> <p>Carbon Sink certification guidelines for complex biomass conversion processes (co)producing biochar or other long-term carbon storing material.</p> <p>Know-how on biochar application in (fruit) trees.</p>	<p>Development and testing of novel biochar production methods.</p> <p>Improvement of biorefinery approaches.</p> <p>Promoting PyCCS by linking biochar and biofuel production.</p>	<p>Industrial & Research Organizations,</p> <p>Universities,</p> <p>SMEs,</p> <p>Private and public sector.</p>
<p>REACH</p> <p>Consultancy, Coaching and Training related to the innovation in NET-Fuels developments & framework and their Exploitation.</p> <p>Project development know-how to be exploited as a service.</p> <p>Research Data Management and Exploitation strategies to be exploited in further projects.</p>	<p>Engineering; Energy, Biofuels and Renewable Energy Sectors.</p> <p>Research & Innovation Projects; Private company development projects; European and Intercontinental project initiatives.</p> <p>New knowledge on negative-emissions biofuel production and CO2 valorisation as services' knowhow.</p>	<p>Industrial & Research Organizations,</p> <p>SMEs community,</p> <p>Private & Public Sector,</p> <p>R&D International Stakeholders.</p>
<p>WRG</p> <p>Enhanced communication and dissemination platform,</p> <p>Project videos,</p> <p>Project development know-how.</p>	<p>Engineering; Energy, Biofuels and Renewable Energy Sectors.</p> <p>Research & Innovation Projects; Private company development projects.</p> <p>European and Intercontinental project initiatives.</p>	<p>Industrial & Research Organizations,</p> <p>SMEs community,</p> <p>Private & Public Sector,</p> <p>R&D International Stakeholders.</p>

Detailed exploitation plans of the individual KERs will be further elaborated in WP6-T6.4, considering the results of the business plans to be defined for NET-Fuels in WP5, guided by REACH with the data provided by the project partners related to the individual KERs.

Within the “Exploitation Living Check-book”, REACH plans to maintain an updated list of the KERs for NET-Fuels (section 5.4.2), with their respective exploitation routes.

5.4 Exploitation Strategy

The Exploitation Strategy for NET-Fuels will describe the activities planned to guarantee the maximum impact and value of the project outcomes, considering the related work packages (WPs) tasks and their interdependencies within the NET-Fuels scenario for its exploitation plan and strategic actions (see Figure 9).

Figure 9: NET-Fuels Scenario for its Exploitation Plan and Strategic Actions.

NET-Fuels Exploitation Strategy’s main aim is to ensure and amplify the impact of the project results, in order to guarantee an effective exploitation impact both during and after the lifetime of the project.

For achieving the exploitation goals, the strategy adopted throughout the project lifetime considers the following aspects and actions listed in Table 5 below.

Table 5: Summary of NET-Fuels Exploitation Strategy

Exploitation Strategy Aspect	Actions to be taken / Outcomes	Means of Achievement
1. NET-Fuels Common KER (Product Results (PR) and Key Exploitation Results (KER) Identification)	<p>For the NET-Fuels Common KER, key-technologies and auxiliary systems will be identified and their combined usage within the KER will be specified in detail.</p> <p>Creation of business model (BM) and business plan (BM), with roadmap to market scale-up.</p> <p>Specific ownership and IP share definition and management.</p> <p>NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book will record the development of this action and its outcomes.</p>	<p>Preliminary and Final Outcomes of the WPs-Tasks: WP6-T6.4; WP5-T5.1, T5.2.</p> <p>Discussions with All Consortium Partners.</p> <p>Workshop guided by REACH to All Consortium for PRs and KERs identification.</p> <p>Support from EC IP Services (IP Scan; IP Helpdesk, etc).</p>
2. NET-Fuels Individual KERs (Product Results (PR) and Key Exploitation Results (KER) Identification)	<p>For each NET-Fuels Individual KER, key-technologies will be identified, together with the partner(s)’ background knowledge involved.</p> <p>Creation of individual (per KER) business models (BM) and business plans (BM), including market roadmaps.</p>	<p>Preliminary and Final Outcomes of the WPs-Tasks: WP6-T6.4; WP5-T5.1, T5.2.</p> <p>Discussions with Consortium Partners.</p>

	<p>Definition of ownerships and IP share management.</p> <p>NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book will record the development of this action and its outcomes.</p>	<p>Workshop guided by REACH to the Consortium for individual KERs identification.</p> <p>Support from EC IP Services (IP Scan; IP Helpdesk, etc).</p>
<p>3. NET-Fuels Exploitation Target Groups / ESAB (Continuous Identification, Enlargement and Networking)</p>	<p>Identification of the Target Groups (general and specific) for enhancing NET-Fuels Exploitation.</p> <p>Enlarging ESAB Members in terms of AB and specific international stakeholders.</p> <p>Synergies with existing R&I projects and related initiatives. Close relationship with NET-Fuels sister-projects from the call HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-09.²</p> <p>NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book will record the development of this action and its outcomes.</p>	<p>Preliminary and Final Outcomes of the WPs-Tasks: WP5-T5.1; WP6- T6.4.</p> <p>Contributions from All Consortium Partners.</p> <p>Support from EC Networks & Hubs.</p> <p>Exploitation Partner & Consortium interaction with Stakeholders via events organization and participation.</p>
<p>4. NET-Fuels Market Research Exploitation (Continuous update for enhancing exploitation opportunities)</p>	<p>Exploitation of the outcomes of the Competing Technologies & Market Research.</p> <p>Identification of the most stakeholders Evaluation / Analysis</p> <p>NET-Fuels Technology Watch Living Document (WP5-T5,1), and the Exploitation Living Check-book (WP6-T6.4) will record the development of this action and its outcomes.</p>	<p>Preliminary and Final Outcomes of the WPs-Tasks: WP5-T5.1; WP6- T6.4.</p> <p>Discussions and Contributions with/from All Consortium Partners.</p> <p>Support from ESAB.</p> <p>Support from EC Networks & Hubs.</p>
<p>5. NET-Fuels Intellectual Property Definition & Management (Continuous update aligned with the project development)</p>	<p>Definition and Management of the PRs and KERs ownership, protection and publication of knowledge.</p> <p>IP Definition for all Partners in relation to their PRs and KERs (individually or jointly owned).</p> <p>IPR Management.</p> <p>NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book will record the development of this action and its outcomes.</p>	<p>Preliminary and Final Outcomes of the WPs-Tasks: WP5 (All Tasks); WP6- T6.4.</p> <p>Discussions with All Consortium Partners.</p> <p>Workshop guided by REACH to All Consortium for PRs and KERs identification.</p> <p>Support from EC IP Services (IP Scan; IP Helpdesk, etc).</p>
<p>6. Exploitation via NET-Fuels Stakeholders Network (Continuous update on the Networking procedures and on the Communities of</p>	<p>Exploitation of NET-Fuels' Stakeholders Network, in close alignment with the Communication and Dissemination Channels established in WP6.</p> <p>Input from (3) NET-Fuels Exploitation Target Groups / ESAB.</p>	<p>Preliminary and Final Outcomes of the WPs-Tasks: WP6 (All Tasks), with support from all technical WPs.</p> <p>Contributions from All Consortium Partners and their networks.</p>

² NET-Fuels sister-projects from the call HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-09 are listed in Annex 2 of this document.

Practice building for the project)	<p>Definition and continuous adaptation of appropriate Networking procedures.</p> <p>Creation of Communities of Practice for the project.</p> <p>Networking at regional, national, European and International levels.</p> <p>Definition of suitable KPIs for the Networking activities for NET-Fuels in total alignment with its dissemination activities.</p> <p>NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book will record the development of this action and its outcomes.</p> <p>NET-Fuels Dissemination tracking records on the project’s social media accounts will also register the progress of its networking activities.</p>	<p>Support from ESAB.</p> <p>Exploitation Partner & Consortium networking and interaction with Stakeholders via social media, virtual and face-to-face events organization and participation.</p> <p>Full alignment with the project’s Dissemination strategy.</p> <p>Dedicated Seminars and Events.</p> <p>Support from EC Networks & Hubs.</p>
7. NET-Fuels overall Exploitation Roadmap (Market Scale-up Roadmap and Leveraging of the experience acquired throughout the project for further research proposals, publications and presentations at conferences)	<p>Exploitation of Common and Individual KERs based on excellence competition (Horizon Europe cluster 4 and cluster 5, low carbon and circular industries) and joint initiatives with industries (e.g. Joint Undertaking, Innovation Fund) at EU level.</p> <p>Exploitation at regional level through ERDF and national initiatives, aiming at meeting Next Generation EU funding and initiatives.</p> <p>NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book will record the development of this action and its outcomes.</p>	<p>Outcomes of the WPs-Tasks: WP5 (All Tasks); WP6 (All Tasks), with support from WP2, WP3 and WP4.</p> <p>Contributions from All Consortium Partners.</p> <p>Support from the NET-Fuels academic partners for the preparation of follow-up project proposals and publications.</p> <p>Support from ESAB.</p> <p>Support from EC Networks & Hubs; especially from the Horizon Results Booster (HRB)³.</p>

Outcomes of the Exploitation Strategy will be monitored and evaluated via the target values defined for the planned KPIs (to be fully defined in future versions of the Exploitation Plan), to ensure that it is achieving the desired results. Adjustments will be performed, whenever needed, both during and after the lifetime of the project.

5.4.1 Identification of NET-Fuels KERs and Value Proposition Definition

As stated in the Summary of the Exploitation Strategy (ES) above (Table 5), Product Results and KERs will be further identified and expanded with respect to the initial list presented in section 5.3.

For the evaluation of business and innovation potential, the preliminary identified KERs will be analyzed by REACH and the project’s Innovation Manager (FRA), from a business and innovation perspective. Each result will be assessed bearing in mind the following pillars: Strength of business idea, target sector and competition issues, target market and customers, stakeholder analysis and financial issues. Those results with potential

³ <https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>

to become products and services will progress to the next step of the EP methodology. The identification of the Background Knowledge for every Project Result / KERs is part of this task.

For this, workshops are planned from REACH to all Consortium Partners (see items (1) and (2) of the ES), to help consolidate NET-Fuels Exploitable Results identification and to discuss those results (PRs, KERs) and to define their Value Proposition.

5.4.2 NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book

REACH will share with the Consortium a living document, named “NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book”, including: the overall *Project Results* and the identified *Key Exploitable Results (KERs)*, also related to the partners background knowledge for their developments.

As stated in the Summary of the Exploitation Strategy (ES) in Table 5, NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book will be shared with the Consortium via the project SharePoint repository, to collect inputs regarding the Project Results, the KERs, the IP definition details and the Exploitable Results. It will record the development of the NET-Fuels Exploitation Strategy’s actions and its outcomes.

The Exploitation Check-book will also maintain an updated list of the organizations connected with the project, including their level of interest and engagement with NET-Fuels’ exploitation.

Figure 10 and Figure 11 show detail in screenshots of the NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book (preliminary version).

Figure 10: Screenshot Detail of the NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book (Guide for Usage).

PR#	Name	Description, related deliverable/s or tasks	Readiness Level at project START*	Readiness Level at project END*	Regime *	Owner/s
			*TRL/ MRL	*TRL/ MRL	* single or joint ownership	
1	Feedstock test: digestate from anaerobic digestion of manure and corn silage	Task 2.1: Feedstock supply, pre treatment and characterization				HSA
2	Feedstock test: calamity wood	Task 2.1: Feedstock supply, pre treatment and characterization				HSA
3	Feedstock test: prunings	Task 2.1: Feedstock supply, pre treatment and characterization				HSA
4	Design parameters of the oxy combustion chamber	Task 2.2: Modelling and design of oxyfuel combustion and heat transfer to FLR				SUI / HSA, ULTAI
5	Design parameters of the heat transfer	Task 2.2: Modelling and design of oxyfuel combustion and heat transfer to FLR				SUI / HSA, ULTAI
6	H2 purity through PSA	Task 2.3: Thermo chemical conversion and oxyfuel combustion tests				HSA
7	Oxy combustion optimization	Task 2.3: Thermo chemical conversion and oxyfuel combustion tests				SUI
8	CO2 purity by condensing water	Task 2.3: Thermo chemical conversion and oxyfuel combustion tests				ULTAI
9	FLR pilot plant upgrade with additional units	Task 2.3: Thermo chemical conversion and oxyfuel combustion tests				HSA, SUI, ULTAI, HINAKA

Figure 11: Screenshot Detail of one sheet of the NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book (preliminary version).

Initially, the data within the Exploitation Check-book will contain the preliminary information of the project Grant Agreement (GA) with small refinements. Further updates on the Exploitation Check-book, including all partners’ review and add-ons, will reflect some elaborated filtering and expansions on the preliminary list of the project’s results and KERs. For this, each partner will be requested to include inputs regarding the Technical Readiness Levels (TRL) of the project results (current and expected TRLs), details of the products’ ownership (individually-owned, jointly-owned), and relevant information for the definition of the exploitation pathway (open, licensed, patents, etc.).

The NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book will be made available to the Consortium in month M7 via the NET-Fuels SharePoint, and will also be useful for the implementation of the Intellectual Property Strategy (preliminarily described in this document, section 5.4.4).

5.4.3 Networking Activities

Besides the Networking and Clustering activities mentioned in the Communication and Dissemination Plan, the exploitation will also profit on excellence competition (Horizon Europe cluster 4 and cluster 5, low carbon and circular industries) and joint initiatives with industries (e.g.: Joint Undertakings⁴ and Innovation Fund⁵, among others), and at regional level through the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)⁶ and related National initiatives, aiming at meeting Next Generation EU⁷ funding and initiatives, as planned in [1]. Academic partners will leverage the experience acquired throughout the project for further research proposals, publications and presentations at conferences.

The ESAB members will meet at least once a year, in coincidence with the General Assembly meetings of the project. Dedicated meetings will be set up after month M13 with selected stakeholders for the definition of the Business Plan.

As defined in the Exploitation Strategy, the following will be carried out in terms of networking activities:

- The Exploitation partner (REACH) will enforce that networking interactions among Consortium members and Stakeholders regularly happen via social media, as well as via virtual and face-to-face events organization and participation. This will be organized in full alignment with the project’s dissemination strategy. Dedicated seminars and events with Stakeholders will also be organized as planned in [1], and will be described in more detail in future versions of the Exploitation Plan.

⁴ Joint Undertakings under Horizon Europe: <https://www.eumonitor.eu/9353000/1/j9vvik7m1c3gyxp/vlgkodah31yz>

⁵ Innovation Fund: https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/programmes/innovation-fund_en

⁶ ERDF: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/funding/erdf_en

⁷ Next Generation EU: https://next-generation-eu.europa.eu/index_en

- REACH will cater for the definition and continuous adaptation of appropriate networking procedures for NET-Fuels, with the creation of Communities of Practice for the project. Networking at regional, national, European and international levels will be encouraged and targeted, following suitably defined KPIs for the Networking activities for NET-Fuels in total alignment with the dissemination tasks.
- The Exploitation Task T6.4 will establish an ecosystem of communities of practice for the project, including industrial partners and interested stakeholders, aiming at promoting the project's identified KERs and disseminating their validation via the represented case studies, so that other interested stakeholders will be able to further engage with the NET-Fuels solution via the organized T6.4 exploitation activities.

The NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book will record the development of this action and its outcomes, and the project's dissemination tracking records on the project's social media accounts will also register the progress of its networking activities on a regular basis.

5.4.4 Intellectual Property Management

In the NET-Fuels Exploitation Strategy (item 5), a detailed Intellectual Property Management description will be provided, aiming to inform the partners about the importance of protecting the project generated data, both individually and collectively.

A specific methodology and strategy in support of the definition and management of the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and Protection within the NET-Fuels project will be defined in detail in the next version of the Exploitation Plan. This will incorporate individual exploitation plans for all KERs (per partner), with cost-benefit feasibility.

IP Activities with the NET-Fuels Consortium: A Workshop is planned, led by REACH, to align and strengthen the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) topic among the Consortium. IPR support services from the EC - European Commission, like IP-Scan within the EC IP Helpdesk⁸, are also encouraged to be followed/undertaken by NET-Fuels project partners.

5.5 Roadmap to Market Uptake

For NET-Fuels Exploitation, all tasks from WP5, which include Technology Watch, Market Analysis, Business Model and Business Plan Development, Regulatory Assessment and System Scale-up Approach, will support the Exploitation Plan and the roadmap formMarket uptake.

NET-Fuels exploitation activities will be focused on the stakeholders' engagement, partners' contacts and collaboration with national and European associations and organisations. WP6 Task T6.4 will receive inputs from WP5-T5.2 and benefit from the market intelligence research analysis performed in WP5-T5.1, which aims to support the project's business development definition and its sustainable scale-up approach at industrial level. T6.4 will also benefit from the outcomes of WP5-T5.2 (Business model development) and WP4-T4.4 (socioeconomic analysis).

The next four sub-sections (5.5.1-5.5.4) briefly describe how the exploitation of the project in relation to its Market Scale-up Roadmap incorporates the contributions of all defined tasks in WP5.

5.5.1 Competitive Research and Technology & Market Analysis

In NET-Fuels the elaboration of the Competitive Research Technology and Market Analysis is dealt within WP5 tasks T5.1 and T5.2.

For the **Competitive Research Technology Analysis**, in order to support the project's business development definition and its sustainable scale-up approach at the industrial level, WP5-Task T5.1 conducts an extensive

⁸ https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/regional-helpdesks/european-ip-helpdesk_en

research analysis to position the NET-Fuels technology. In this task, relevant competitive technologies, such as CCUS, soil carbon sequestration, energy storage, and negative biofuel activities, related to the value proposition defined for NET-Fuels, are seen as the main focus of the Competitive Research and Technology Analysis. Figure 12 (a,b) illustrate the “Technology-Watch” living document produced in T5.1.

The approach to perform the research analysis has led to the following work-procedures:

- Definition of specific keywords to conduct the search.
- Identification of relevant sources (e.g.: projects, articles) via various repositories and databases for scientific publications and projects (e.g.: BASE, CORDIS).
- Identification of relevant patents and technologies with the help of specialized databases (Esp@cenet, EUIPO, WIPO, etc.).
- Identification of the state of the art in science and technology as well as scientific breakthroughs and industrial pioneers.
- Learning from success cases and from failed projects, from which the reasons for failure can serve as risk mitigation measures for the project.
- Implementation of a “Technology-Watch” living document shared with project partners.

Project-	Name	Keywords	Nation	Partners	Status	Link	Input from
1	Bell Bay Powerfuels Project	Methanol	Australia	ABEL Energy, Thyssenkrupp	Early Development	https://www.abelenergy.com.au/our-projects	REACH
2	FT-Biofuels in Austria	Biofuel	Austria	Austrian Bioenergy Centre GmbH	In Operation	https://nachhaltigwirtschaften.at/en/edz/projects/ft-	REACH
3	Vienna Green CO2	CCS from exhaust gases	Austria	TU-Wien, BOKU, Shell, Bertsch, MTEC,	In Planning	https://www.energy-innovation-	REACH
4	Antwerp@C	CCS	Belgium	Air Liquide, BASF, Borealis,	Early Development	https://newsroom.portofantwerpbruges.com/antwerp-	REACH
5	Carbon Connect Delta	CCS	Belgium	Smart Delta Resources, Authority North	In Planning	https://www.smartdeltaresources.com/en/carbon-	REACH
6	H2BE	H2 from Natural Gas, CCS, Blue H2	Belgium	Engie, Equinor	In Planning	https://gems.engie.com/business-news/engie-equinor-	REACH
7	Kairos@C	CCS, Liquify	Belgium	Air Liquide, BASF	In Planning	https://kairosatc.eu/	REACH
8	North CCU Hub	CCS	Belgium	North Sea Port, Provincie Oost-	Early Development	https://northccuhub.eu/	REACH
9	North CCU Methanol	CCS, Methanol	Belgium		Early Development	https://northccuhub.eu/north-c-	REACH
10	Power to Methanol Antwerp BV	CCS, Methanol	Belgium	ENGIE, Fluxys, Indaver, INOVYN,	Advanced Development	https://powertomethanolantwerp.com/	REACH
11	Steelanol	CCS, Bio-Ethanol	Belgium	ArcelorMittal, Primetals, LanzaTech,	Advanced Development	http://www.steelanol.eu/en	REACH
12	Haru Oni	DAC, PTM, MTF, PTF	Chile	Enel, Enap, Empresas Gasco, Johnson	In Operation	https://www.haruoni.com/#/en	REACH
13	Bio-Rafinery-Project	CCS, Energy, Bio-Energy	Croatia	INA	Early Development	https://onlineibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1111/gcbb.127	REACH
14	CCGeo	CCS, Geothermal, Power, Heat	Croatia	AAT Geothermie, CLEAG	Advanced Development	https://climate.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-	REACH
15	Petrokemija Kutina	CCS, Blue Ammonia	Croatia	Petrokemija, INA	In Planning	http://www.enos-project.eu/media/22619/068_final-with-	REACH
16	Bifrost	CCS, CCOS	Denmark	TotalEnergies, Noreco, Nordsefonden,	In Planning	https://www.carboncapturejournal.com/news/ccs-project-	REACH
17	Greensand	CCS, CCOS	Denmark	Wintershall Dea, INEOS Oil, Energy	Early Development	https://www.projectgreensand.com/en/	REACH
18	SHARC	CCS, Blue H2	Finland	Neste	Early Development	https://www.neste.com/releases-and-	REACH
19	Cryocap	CCS, Blue H2	France	AirLiquide	In Operation	https://enjinering.airliquide.com/world-premiere-air-	REACH
20	Grandpuits: a zero-crude	Biofuel, BTL, Bioplastic,	France	TotalEnergies	Advanced Development	https://totalenergies.com/expertise-	REACH
21	BlueHyNow	CCS, CCOS, Blue H2, reforming natural	Germany	Wintershall Dea, Nord-West Oelleitung	In Planning	https://wintershalldea.com/en/newsroom/wintershall-	REACH
22	CAC SYN-FUEL	CCS, PTM, MTF	Germany	CAC	In Operation	https://www.cac-synfuel.com/en/	REACH
23	H2GE FOSTEK	CCS, reforming natural Gas, Blue H2,	Germany	Equinor, VNG AG	In Planning	https://vng.de/en/newsroom/2022-07-04-equinor-and-vng-	REACH
24	H2morrow	CCS, Blue H2, reforming natural Gas,	Germany	Equinor, OGE, Stell Europe	In Planning	https://oge.net/en/sustainable/projects-our-hydrogen-	REACH
25	INTERACT	PTF	Germany	INTERACT	In Operation	https://ineract.de/en/home/	REACH
26	Westküste 100 / OXYFUEL100	CCS, Blue H2, Methanol,	Germany	EDF Germany, Holcim Germany, Ørsted	In Planning	https://www.westkueste100.de/	REACH
27	Coda Terminal	CCS, CCMS	Iceland	Carbfix, Dan-Unity CO2	Early Development	https://www.carbfix.com/codaterminal	REACH
28	Orca	CCS, DAC	Iceland	ClimeWorks, Carbfix	In Operation	https://climeworks.com/roadmap/orca	REACH
29	Silverstone	CCS, CCMS	Iceland	Carbfix, OnPower	In Operation	https://climate.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-	REACH
30	CCS Ravenna Hub	CCS	Italy	Eni	Early Development	https://ccshub.ogcl.com/focus_hubs/ravenna/	REACH
31	Cleankerk	CCS, CaL, RCC	Italy	LEAP, CSIC, VIZ, Politecnico di Milano,	Early Development	http://www.cleanker.eu/	REACH
32	H2M	CCS, Blue H2, reforming natural Gas,	Netherlands	Vattenfall, Equinor, Gasunie	Early Development	https://group.vattenfall.com/nl/en/SysSiteAssets/vattenf	REACH
33	Araqmis	Storage, Transport	Netherlands	TotalEnergies, Shell, EBN, Gasunie	Early Development	https://www.aramis-ccs.com/	REACH
34	Driven CO2 Plant	CCS, RW	Netherlands	AVR Waste Processing BV, Air Liquide	In Operation	https://www.avr.nl/en/co2-installation/first-tons-of-co2-	REACH
35	H-Vision	CCS, Blue H2, reforming natural Gas,	Netherlands	Deltalings, Air Liquide, bp, EBN,	Early Development	https://www.h-vision.nl/en	REACH
36	L10 CCS	Storage, Transport, CCOS	Netherlands	Neptune Energy, EBN Capital B.V.,	Early Development	https://www.neptuneenergy.com/sites/neptuneenergy-	REACH

Figure 12a,b: Screenshots detail of the „Technology-Watch” living document available in NET-Fuels SharePoint

Through this transparent approach for the elaboration of the technology watch, the partners will be able to interact within the living document available in the project's repository, with contribution of inputs and relevant comments.

Considering the **Market Analysis for NET-Fuels** project, an approach considering the Product Results (PRs) and Key-Exploitable Results (KERs), combined with the competitive technologies directly related to them is being developed within WP5, so that potential risks related to the KERs can be identified and strategies to overcome them can be timely provided.

The approach taken for the initial NET-Fuels market analysis will provide useful information for the Exploitation Strategy defined for NET-Fuels, in the following way:

- Performance of a SWOT Analysis [4] of each relevant competitive technology in comparison with the NET-Fuels technology, considering factors that are internal (strengths and weaknesses) and external (opportunities and threats). This analysis will provide important input for defining the NET-Fuels technology market position, in face of the identified potential competitors.
- Performance of a PESTEL Analysis⁹ (also called PESTLE¹⁰ with original concept described in [3]) will provide an overview of the macro-environmental factors, namely: Political, Economic, Sociological, Technological, Legal and Environmental, that may have an influence in the NET-Fuels market analysis. As a strategic tool for understanding market growth/decline as well as business position, PESTEL will be especially useful in this analysis to identify potential markets.

5.5.2 Business Models and Business Plans

In NET-Fuels the creation of Business Models and Business Plans is dealt within WP5-T5.2. Business Models (BM) are planned for exploiting the Key Exploitable Results (KERs). Business Models Canvas (BMC) [5], in their Sustainable Version [6], will be used to design BMs for each KER. The BMC embeds: the value proposition (value proposition and sustainability benefits), customers (customer relationships, channels, customer segments, beneficiaries), financial model (cost structure, revenue streams), and capabilities (key activities, key partners, key resources). Due to its simplicity, it will allow the partners to visualize the most important aspects of their developed products in relation to their business potential.

The definition of the Business Models will provide essential information for the overall Business Plan development of the project and will provide significant inputs for the exploitation activities of the project, also taking into consideration aspects of NET-Fuels' socio-economic analysis (T4.4).

KERs Individual Exploitation Plans: As a consequence of the KERs Business Models, Individual Exploitation Plans will be defined for selected Key Exploitable Results. This task will demand intensive interaction with the involved NET-Fuels project partners, since each partner has different goals and perspectives for their developed products within the project, the potential project's advances, services, know-how, and work experience.

NET-Fuels Business Plan: A Business Plan (BP) will be developed for the overall common KER related to the developed NET-Fuels technology, to showcase the business potential of the technology and to define the tactics to achieve the defined goals. The Business Plan development will take into consideration all the relevant information from the market and competitive research analysis (potential market size, competitive technologies), and from the NET-Fuels overall common Business Model (potential end-users, cost structure, channels). NET-Fuels BP will also assess the project's results (development status, potential impact, innovation potential, IPR issues) and social and economic impacts. An analysis of the level of competition in the negative biofuels industry will be conducted to determine how its long-term profitability is affected.

⁹ PESTEL: <https://www.professionalacademy.com/blogs/marketing-theories-pestel-analysis/>

¹⁰ PESTLE: <https://libguides.library.usyd.edu.au/c.php?g=508107&p=5994242>

Hence, the Business Plan will bring preliminary commercialization strategies, risk assessment and financial projections to the project.

5.5.3 Regulatory Assessment

The regulatory framework for the project scale-up process will be assessed within WP5-T5.3 (led by UNIBO), taking into account the market research analysis scope. A list of requirements and priorities will be defined, related to methane grid injection, biochar certification, industrial emissions, water management, among others.

Project specific plant configurations may also require further investigation, for instance, in hydrogen storage and compression, incentives and schemes in specific countries or geographic areas.

A database or document will be compiled, considering input management (regulations and requirements to handle the feedstock, end-of-waste), processing (e.g., emission limit levels), product quality (e.g., H₂ standards, biochar certification), type of legislation, jurisdiction, subject/field of application, risks and barrier and carbon accounting (both for the process and for the use of biochar in soils for carbon sequestration).

During the entire duration of this task, implementation will be followed, and interventions made where needed to examine specific problems and issues. A dedicated session or joint consortium meeting session will be organized to present the findings (M5.4, M30).

5.5.4 System Scale-up Approach

Scale-up strategies of the integrated NET-Fuels technology system for industrial level will be evaluated by WP5-T5.4, led by FRA. The aim is to provide energy and material balances, industry-scale sizing of major units, estimation of the overall cost, process conversions, energy consumption, and waste stream production.

The results of the operation at pilot scale (WP2 and WP3) will serve to analyze process parameters and yields as a basis to estimate the cost efficiency of the process. These data sets will be joined with process and operational data provided from industrial partners like refineries. Then, concepts for scale-up will be developed, consisting in the definition of feasible guidelines (a roadmap) for a sustainable scale-up approach at industrial level of the project, and the identification of appropriate and diversified case studies to validate the overall NET-Fuels system. The final cost assessment will serve as input for design optimization in the scale-up phase.

5.6 Exploitation Management & Monitoring

The exploitation management for NET-Fuels project will follow the defined Exploitation Strategy and will consider several aspects related to: the dissemination of the project results; the identified stakeholders and potential end-users; the interaction among project partners, end-users and stakeholders; the interaction with the NET-Fuels Advisory Board members and their institutions; and the networking procedure to be adopted within this scenario.

The Exploitation Control Mechanism (ECM) to be adopted embeds: (1) the steps of the Exploitation Strategy and its KPIs (still to be further defined); (2) the NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book containing details about the Project Results (PRs) and the KERs; and (3) the Market Scale-up Roadmap and its driving parameters.

According to the EC, the Beneficiaries of the Horizon Europe are responsible for the Exploitation outcomes for at least two years after the end of the project. As the partner responsible for the Exploitation, REACH will monitor the Exploitation Results by keeping track of all activities both during and beyond the lifetime of the project, aligned with the Horizon Results Booster (HRB) requirements. Figure 13 illustrates the preliminary plan for NET-Fuels Exploitation Management and Monitoring.

Figure 13: Preliminary NET-Fuels Exploitation Management & Monitoring Plan.

5.7 Exploitation Concluding Remarks

The preliminary Exploitation Plan (EP) for delivered in month M6 within D6.2 describes how the exploitation tasks will be led and structured within NET-Fuels implementation phase, considering: the general exploitation objectives; the initial exploitation strategy; the expected impacts (technical, socio-economic and environmental); the planned tasks and activities; and the initial steps for the intellectual property definition among partners and respective IPR management.

As shown in Figure 1 (overall Plan of NET-Fuels Deliverables and lead partners) of this document (D6.2), updates on the EP are planned to be included in deliverable D6.3 (First Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Report) in M16, and in D6.4 (Scale-up of the integrated NET-Fuels technology system for industrial level) in M36. Moreover, reports about the dissemination and exploitation activities of the project will be included in the technical parts of the project reports RP1, RP2 and RP3, respectively planned for covering the periods of: RP1 (M1 - M18) with submission on June 2024; RP2 (M19 - M36) with submission on December 2025; and RP3 (M37 - M48) with submission on October 2026, as defined in [1,2].

The main target is that the NET-Fuels Exploitation Strategy will ensure and amplify the impact of the project results to guarantee effective exploitation during and after the lifetime of the project.

6 Conclusions

This document describes the strategy and activities of the NET-Fuels project with respect to communication, dissemination, and exploitation of project outputs to maximise impact, whilst creating pathways to follow-up developments and collaborations to take the technology to pre-commercial scale and, ultimately, commercial adoption. This plan described herein represents a first draft and will be updated at least annually as new information and opportunities arise.

7 References

- [1] Horizon Europe Project NET-Fuels - Grant Agreement Number: 101083780, associated with document Ref. Ares(2022)7097679 - 13/10/2022.
- [2] Horizon Europe Project NET-Fuels Nr.: 101083780 - Deliverable D1.1: Project management plan, associated with document Ref. Ares(2022)9015439 - 30/12/2022.
- [3] Aguilar, F. (1967). Scanning the business environment. MacMillan Co, 1967.
- [4] HBR. (2005). Strategy: Create and Implement the best strategy for your business. USA: Harvard Business School Press, 2005.
- [5] Osterwalder, A., Pigneur, Y., & Clark, T. (2010). Business Model Generation: A Handbook for Visionaries, Game Changers, and Challengers. Strategyzer, 2010.
- [6] The Blue Tribe Company. (2017). Retrieved from <https://bluetribe.co/business-model-innovation-the-secret-weapon-of-your-sustainability-strategy>, 2017.
- [7] Horizon Europe Project NET-Fuels Nr.: 101083780 - Deliverable D1.2: NET-Fuels Data Management plan, 30/04/2023.

Gantt Chart 2a: Short-term communication and dissemination plan to end of 2023 (similar will be produced for each project year)

This Gantt chart will be discussed with project partners over the course of 2023 and refined and updated as necessary.

Short-term DC&E Plan (to end 2023)

Top Level Activity	Task	Partner inputs	2023											
			May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec				
D&C scoping and stakeholder definition with partners	WP8 discussion meeting	WRG, REACH, UniBo												
	Define potential stakeholders and industrial networks	All: Input to list												
	Define other related projects for clustering	All: Input to list												
	Finalise engagement and clustering actions for 2023	WRG, REACH, UniBo												
Website and Digital Media	Consortium input into requirements for written media (flyers, brochure etc.)	All: Requirements												
	Create flyers/posters for different audiences	All: Feedback and comments												
	Create project brochure	All: Feedback and comments												
	Storyboard for a motion graphics/infographics video	All: Feedback and comments												
	Create motion graphics/infographics video	All: Sign off of final video												
	Storyboard for "Talking Heads" Q&A video	All: Feedback and comments												
	Create "Talking heads" video with Q&A about the project	WP leads for interviews. Sign off from partners												
	Activate website area for public reports and deliverables	N/A												
	Activate website area for all digital media	N/A												
Create a project newsletter (including partner contributions)	All: Input on content, feedback, and sign-off													
Conferences and Events	Define events for NETFuels participation	All: Review partner presentations/publications (if applicable)												
	Project review meeting	All: Attendance												
Publications and papers	Define journals and magazines for publishing articles	All: Review publication												

Gantt Chart 2b: Short-term exploitation plan to end of 2023 (similar will be produced for each project year)

Top Level Specific Exploitation Activities	Tasks	Partner inputs	2023									
			7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14		
			May	June	July	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec		
	Months											
NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book	The NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book will be made available via the NET-Fuels SharePoint for receiving inputs about PRs, KERs, BGs + ESAB updates	All – Feedback and guided input (from M7 onwards)										
NET-Fuels Common KER Identification	Workshop on Common KER - Product (PR) and Key Exploitation Results (KER) Identification	All – Attendance & Feedback (estimated for M12)										
NET-Fuels Individual KERs Identification	Workshop on Individual KERs - Product (PRs) and Key Exploitation Results (KERs) Identification	All – Attendance & Feedback (estimated for M11)										
NET-Fuels Intellectual Property Definition	Workshop on Intellectual Property Definition & Management of IPR for NET-Fuels PRs& KERs	All – Attendance & Feedback (estimated for M13)										
NET-Fuels KERs Business Models	Discussions & Virtual Meetings with Partners for preliminary definition of KERs Business Models	All – Requirements and Feedback (estimated to start on 2023 M14)										
Interaction with ESAB Members & NET-Fuels	ESAB selected stakeholders dedicated meetings with NET-Fuels partners for the definition Business Plans	REACH, UNIBO & Selected Partners (estimated to start on 2023 M13)										

Annex 2: NET-Fuels sister-projects from the call HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-09.

Horizon Europe Call: Sustainable, secure and competitive energy supply (HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03) / HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-09 - Carbon-negative sustainable biofuel production.

Horizon Europe Call: Sustainable, secure and competitive energy supply (HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03)		HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-09 - Carbon-negative sustainable biofuel production		
#	ACCEPTED PROJECTS - TITLES:	ACRONYM	PROJECT ID	CORDIS URL / WEBSITE
1	Carbon Negative Biofuels from Organic Waste	CARBIOW	101084443	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101084443 LINK WEBSITE
2	Increasing biomass conversion efficiency to carbon-negative sustainable biofuels by combination of thermal and bio-electrochemical processes	NET-Fuels	101083780	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101083780 LINK WEBSITE
3	Capture and Reuse Of biogenic gases for Negative-emission - sustainable bioFuels	CRONUS	101084405	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101084405 LINK WEBSITE
4	Circular fuel supply for air transport via negative emission HTL conversion	CIRCULAIR	101083944	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101083944 LINK WEBSITE